

which showed their relative non-toxicity. These compounds, when tested for their antielectroshock seizure protection and anorexigenic activities at 1/5th of the ALD_{50} , were found inactive. They, however, affected the animals in their gross CNS behaviour. In general, all of them induced stimulations on CNS (SMA and reactivity increased) and writhing. Hypothermia ranged between 0.4 to 1.6°. Results are discussed in Table 3.

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Piperazine-1,4-bis-Salts of 2-mercapto, 3,6,8-trisubstituted-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones as Anti-inflammatory Agents

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1,4-SUBSTITUTED-PIPERAZINE compounds have been reported¹ to possess potent anti-inflammatory activity. Further, a potent anti-inflammation in some quinazolinones is well

established². 'Thiol' group containing compounds have, further, been found to possess enhanced anti-inflammatory activity³. These observations led us to prepare piperazine-1,4-bis-salts of 2-mercapto, 3,6,8-trisubstituted-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones as anti-inflammatory agents.

Experimental

*Aryl(Alkyl)-isothiocyanates*⁴, *5-Bromo-anthranilic acid* and *3,5-dibromo-anthranilic Acid*⁵; *5-Iodoanthranilic acid*⁶ and *3,5-Dichloro-anthranilic acid*⁷ were prepared by the conventional methods. *2-Mercapto-3-aryl(alkyl)-6,8-disubstituted-quinazolinones* have been synthesised by the procedure given by Dave *et al*⁸.

Piperazine-1,4, bis-salts of 2-mercapto-3,6,8-trisubstituted-quinazolin-4(3H)-one were prepared by the method earlier reported by us⁹. The absence of a peak at 2550-2600 cm^{-1} indicates for the utilization of SH group in final step, forming salt with piperazine. A peak at 1500 cm^{-1} also confirms the formation of aforesaid amine salts. See Table-1 for relevant data of these piperazine 1,4-bis salts of the corresponding 2-mercapto-quinazolinones.

TABLE 1—PIPERAZINE-1,4-BIS-SALTS OF 2-MERCAPTO-3,6,8-TRISUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLIN-4(3H)-ONES

Compound Nos.	R	m.p. °C	ALD_{50} (mg/kg.wt. of mice)	Percentage protection
		$X^1 = X_2 = H$		
1.	$-C_6H_{11}$	292-293	316	8.4%
2.	$-C_6H_5$	266-68		
3.	$p.CH_3.C_6H_4-$	242-244		
4.	$p.OCH_3.C_6H_4-$	235-236	1000	93.7%
		$X^1 = X^2 = Br$		
5.	$-C_6H_{11}$	290-292	100	34.2%
6.	$-C_6H_5$	> 300		
7.	$p.CH_3.C_6H_4-$	> 300		
8.	$p.OCH_3.C_6H_4-$	298-300		
		$X^1 = X^2 = Cl$		
9.	$-C_6H_{11}$	199-200	464	30.4%
10.	$p.CH_3.C_6H_4-$	267-68		
		$X^1 = H ; X^2 = Br$		
11.	$-C_6H_{11}$	245-46		
12.	$-C_6H_5$	285-86		
13.	$p.CH_3.C_6H_4-$	295-96		
14.	$p.OCH_3.C_6H_4-$	> 300	> 1000	28.4%
		$X^1 = H, X^2 = I$		
15.	$-C_6H_{11}$	298-99	262	43.6%
16.	$-C_6H_5$	252-53		
17.	$p.CH_3.C_6H_4-$	> 300		
18.	$p.OCH_3.C_6H_4-$	> 300		

The m.p are uncorrected. Analyses for N, O, H and S gave percentage error- $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical values.

Pharmacology :

Six of the final compounds were screened out for their effects on the central nervous system and their anti-inflammatory activity in mice. The approximate lethal doses in 50% of animals tested (ALD_{50})¹⁰ were also determined (Table 1). The compounds are relatively non-toxic except compound No. 5. All the compounds tested are CNS excitants at 1/5th of ALD_{50} . The anti-inflammatory activity¹¹ at 1/5th of ALD_{50} ranged between 8.4% to 43.6% protection of mice against carrageenin induced inflammation.

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Sterols of *Melitodes ornata**

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CONFIRMATION of spasmogenic activity in the ethanolic extract of the coral *Melitodes ornata*¹ (Family : Melitoides) prompted us to undertake its chemical investigation. The benzene soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract in which the activity was concentrated was chromatographed on

silica gel column. No pure compound was, however, obtained by this procedure. The benzene soluble fraction was, therefore, treated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide according to the method of Bergmann and Co-workers². The non-saponifiable fraction, so obtained, was chromatographed on silica gel column. Elution with benzene gave a fraction which on recrystallization from methanol gave a crystalline material(M), m.p. 130-32°, which, when examined on silica gel TLC plates impregnated with silver nitrate³; solvent system(1): chloroform: ethylacetate: acetic acid (97: 2. 3: 0.5 v/v) and solvent system (2): chloroform: hexane: acetic acid (25: 27: 0.5 v/v) and spraying reagent: 0.2% solution of dibromofluorescein in 96% ethanol exhibited four fluorescent spots under UV light, demonstrating thus the presence of four compounds in the crystalline material(M). The material(M) was then treated with acetic anhydride-pyridine to give a mixture of acetates which was resolved through the bromo derivatives to yield the following four compounds. Compound A(C₂₈H₄₆O) (M⁺386), m.p., 145-46°, [α]_D-64° (chloroform); compound B (C₂₇H₄₆O) (M⁺386), m.p. 140-42°, [α]_D-39.2° (chloroform); compound C (C₂₉H₅₀O) (M⁺414), m.p. 136°, [α]_D-35° (chloroform) and compound D (C₂₈H₄₈O) (M⁺400), m.p. 152-53°, [α]_D-34.6° (chloroform). The physical and chemical constants of compound A, compound B, compound C and compound D were very close to the sterols, brassicasterol⁴, cholesterol⁵, β -sitosterol⁷ and campesterol⁸ respectively. The identity was finally established by comparison (m.p. UV, IR, NMR, Mass and TLC) with the known data of the corresponding sterols.

The isolated sterols from the benzene soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract of *M. ornata* do not substantiate its spasmogenic activity.

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